

SOIL POLLUTION BY HOUSEHOLD WASTE AND ITS CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract. *The article provides information on soil pollution, which has become a global problem worldwide today. Contamination of soils around household waste dumps with heavy metals (such as lead, bismuth, nickel, and cadmium) significantly affects the activity of soil microorganisms. These effects have negative consequences for the composition of microorganisms, their biochemical processes, and the overall health of the soil. As a result of burning household waste, Cd and Pb accumulate in the soil, and their concentrations increase over the years. Analysis of soil samples taken from the southern, eastern, northern, and western parts of the study area showed that the amount of heavy metals in the eastern and western parts of the study area is higher than in the southern and northern parts. In the studies, the content of cadmium (Cd) in soil samples MCHJ -1.1 and MCHSha- 1,1, MCHShi-1, MCHG '-1 changed in the amount of 0.11, 0.46, 0.08, 0.06 mg/kg, and it was found that the content of this substance exceeded the clarke (0.13) only from the point MCHSha- 1,1. Cd increased significantly only in the MCHSHA-1.1 zone. It was established that the content of lead (Pb) at all points exceeds the Clarke value (16) by 2-3.5 times. MCHG-1 and MCHSHA-1.1 increased by 3.5 times, MCHJ-1.1 and MCHSHi-1 - by 2 times, and these indicators are close to the background soil indicators.*

Keywords: *soil fertility, pollution, heavy metals, indicators.*

INTRODUCTION

Soil fertility is directly related to its physicochemical properties, humus cover, organic and mineral substances, especially the number and biological activity of various beneficial microorganisms. In addition, it is necessary to purposefully select crops depending on the location of agriculture at different geographical latitudes, the peculiarities of its development, and the creation of modern harmless biotechnologies.

The influence of soil pollutants on nitrogen-containing bacteria is insignificant, and an increase in their number leads to a decrease in soil contamination. Another group of soil microorganisms is very sensitive to household waste contamination, and their task is to preserve and restore soil fertility [Abdraxmanov *at al.* 2023]. Heavy metal contamination is a global problem due to the health risks associated with metal contamination. Although many metals are essential for life, they can be toxically harmful to humans, animals, plants, and microorganisms. The occurrence of heavy metals in the soil is mainly associated with the natural weathering of parent rocks rich in metals and anthropogenic activities such as industry, mining, and agriculture. Here, the influence of soil microbes on the biosorption and bioavailability of heavy metals; the mechanisms of sequestration of heavy metals by plants and microbes; the influence of pollution

on the diversity and activity of soil microbes are considered [Nafiu Abdu *et al.* 2017; Xue-Ting Bai *et al.* 2020].

It is known that household waste is completely different from industrial waste, industrial waste is easy to separate into fractions, while household waste is somewhat difficult to separate into fractions due to its complex composition. For example, it contains various fine fractions, heavy metals, and various food residues, which, on the one hand, are of interest as secondary materials, and on the other hand, their separation using any mechanical devices is a complex process [Juvalikyan X.S. *et al.* 2009]. The presence of heavy metals in the soil around household waste storage areas and landfills has been identified. High concentrations of heavy metals are characteristic of Mg, Zn, Cu, Mo, Se, Cd, and other elements. Copper, mercury, and sulfur are characterized by significantly higher concentrations compared to the maximum permissible concentration (MPC), while slightly higher concentrations of zinc, lead, chromium, copper, and tin decrease with distance from the polygon. The amount of heavy metals in the vertical cross-section of the soil cover is somewhat higher in the upper layers of the soil compared to the lower ones, which is explained by the fact that waste ash, rich in heavy metals, enters the soil cover through the atmosphere during the burning and open storage of waste. It is explained by an increase in the content of zinc, lead, chromium, and copper [Jabbarov Z *et al.* 2024].

The distribution of cadmium, lead, and zinc in the exchange, organic, and 2M HNO₃-extractive fractions, as well as the influence of the concentration of heavy metals on soil microflora, were studied. The concentration of all metals increased with distance from the source of pollution. In the exchange fraction, the concentrations of Cd and Zn were higher than in the organically bound fraction, and a reverse trend was revealed in the Pb transformation. All measured parameters of microbial activity in the soil were influenced by the concentration of heavy metals. The decrease in CFU was most pronounced in the case of oligotrophic bacteria and spore-forming bacteria. Significant inhibition of S-biomass was observed in soils heavily contaminated with heavy metals. With increasing soil contamination, the C_{biomass}:C_{ox} ratio decreased. In general, the values of enzymatic activity in the soil were highest above the source of pollution and decreased as they approached the source of pollution. The obtained results show that a number of parameters of microorganism activity can be used as good indicators of the increase in the concentration of Cd, Pb, and Zn in the soil [M. Šmejkalová *et al.* 2003; Mathiyazhagan Narayanan *et al.*, 2023].

When studying the influence of the types and presence of heavy metals on the microbial activity of the soil by the Cu/Zn contamination gradient, it was established that the microbial biomass and enzyme activity of soil contaminated with Cu and Zn changed. The results showed that the increase in metal levels negatively affected the microbial biomass. The microbial biomass-C (C_{mic})/organic C (C_{org}) ratio was closely related to heavy metal stress. A negative correlation was observed between the biomass of microorganisms in the soil, phosphatase activity, and the assimilation of heavy metals. The activity of soil microorganisms can be predicted using empirical models containing Cu and Zn [Wang Yuan-peng *et al.*, 2007]. Studies were conducted to assess the influence of Cd, Cr, Cu, Ni, Pb, or Zn on the decomposition of organic matter in the soil and their microflora. All the metals stopped the release of CO₂ from the two soils. Among the heavy metals, the influence of Cd, Cu, and Ni is very noticeable, while Pb is the least significant. The toxicity of heavy metals to colony formation by soil bacteria is high for Cd and Cu, which significantly inhibits CO₂ release.

The content of water-soluble heavy metals in gley soil is higher than in light-colored Andosol, and the decrease in CO₂ release is associated with an increase in the content of water-soluble heavy metals, which is divided by the ED values of heavy metals relative to the formation of colonies by bacteria [Hiroyuki Hattori, 1992]. The impact of long-term heavy metal contamination on biological processes in the soil and microbial communities in the soil was studied at a typical electrical coating site in Zhangjiaku, China. The soil of the galvanoplastics plant in Zhangjiakou is heavily polluted with Cr, Cr (VI), Ni, Cu, and Zn, with concentrations ranging from 112.8 to 9727.2, from 0 to 1083.3, from 15.6 to 58.4, from 10.8 to 510.0, and from 69.6 to 631.6 mg/kg, respectively. Soil urease and phosphatase activity significantly decreased as a result of heavy metal contamination, and the carbon content of the microbial biomass and the richness of the bacterial community were significantly lower compared to uncontaminated samples, which indicates that long-term heavy metal contamination had a serious negative impact on soil microorganisms [Wen-Jing Gong *et al.*, 2021].

The potential environmental hazard index of six heavy metals for soil and the environment was assessed as Cd > Cu > Pb > Ni > Zn > V. Cd has high potential environmental hazard, Cu has medium potential environmental hazard, and Zn, Pb, V, and Ni have low potential environmental hazard. The results of a comprehensive assessment of the Hackanson Potential Environmental Risk Index showed that Zone I has a high level of potential risk, zones II, III, and IV have a medium level of risk, and zones V, VI, and VII have a low level of risk. In addition, microbial biomass carbon (MBC) was assessed as having a significant negative correlation or a highly significant negative correlation with 6 heavy metals, and the microbial metabolism coefficient (MMC) was assessed as having a significant positive correlation or a highly significant positive correlation with 6 heavy metals [Bi Tang *et al.*, 2022; Ivan Sazykin *et al.*, 2023]. Soil contamination with heavy metals leads to excessive accumulation of heavy metals in rice and other food crops.

This causes serious damage to the environment and human health. In recent years, great attention has been paid to environmentally friendly cultivation methods using soil microorganisms, reducing the biological absorption of heavy metals in the soil, increasing the resistance of rice to heavy metals, and reducing the transfer of heavy metals from the roots to the above-ground parts of the plant [Jie Liu *et al.*, 2011]. Today, microorganisms resistant to heavy metals mainly consist of bacteria and fungi, the mechanisms of which include: the absorption of heavy metals by microorganisms, the release of growth-stimulating substances, changes in the physicochemical properties of the soil and the composition of the microbial community, changes in the method of transportation of heavy metals in the soil, as well as an improvement in the antioxidant capacity of rice. [Yangbin Mao *et al.*, 2022]. In areas of increased soil contamination with heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Zn, Cu), the ratio of microbial biomass carbon to oxidized carbon has significantly decreased [Michaela F. 2010].

Methods

The Tashkent region is located in the northeastern part of the republic, between the Syr Darya and the Western Tian Shan mountains. The northwestern part coincides with the border between Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, passing through the Karzhantau and Ugam ranges. The border with Kyrgyzstan on the eastern edge passes through the Talas Alatau, Pskem, and Chatkal mountains. The Kurama Range separates it from the Fergana Valley. The hydrogeological conditions of the study area depend on climatic and geomorphological conditions, the lithological composition of permeable rocks, and the structural features of the studied area. undefined For the studies, soil samples were taken from the southern part (MCHJ -1.1 0-14) E 069° 28'42236":N

41°05'22348", eastern part (MCHSha- 1,1) E 069° 28'5935":N 41°05'0668": northern part (MCHShi-1) E 069° 29'21393":N 41°05'47208" and western part (MCHG'-1) E 69°27'36.5"N 41°05'30.7" coordinates.

The amount of pollutants in the soil was determined by inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) and the obtained results were compared according to Binogradov's Clarke classification.

Research results. The soils of the study area are mainly dryland and typical sierozem soils of irrigated lands, which make up 28-40% of the soils of the Akhangaran district, these soils are mainly medium loamy, non-dense, light gray, cloddy. Ash particles formed as a result of the combustion of waste are encountered. Fragments of glass, gravel, and fragments of polyethylene can be found. White carbonates can be seen. In the area where the soil profile was taken, winter wheat and corn were sown, and insect burrows and plant roots were found. Transitioned to the next layer with a change in color. Plastics, metals, food waste, paper, textiles, and chemical substances accumulated in household waste dumps release organic and inorganic substances during decomposition. When these substances mix with the soil solution, they change the reaction (pH). Biochemical processes in the soil, such as decomposition, oxidation, and ammonification, are intensified under the influence of natural factors, leading to changes in chemical processes, reactions, and pH environment within the soil.

Table 1

Changes in the pH of contaminated soils

Soil processes	Exposure to pollutants	pH change
Decomposition of organic waste residues (fermentation, ammonification, fermentation, fermentation)	Ammonium, carbonates, cations are released	The pH rises towards the alkaline environment.
Some chemical waste, such as batteries, metal scraps	Heavy metals, sulfates, nitrates, chlorides are released	pH decreases towards acidity
Long-term waste accumulation	Salts accumulate, humus decomposes	Alkalinization - A shift to an alkaline environment occurs

Changes in the pH of soils around household waste disposal sites disrupt the balance of nutrients and alter the mobility of heavy metals (they dissolve less in alkaline environments and more in acidic environments, transferring to plants). This leads to environmental consequences, such as changes in the composition of microorganisms (a decrease in beneficial microbes, an increase in humus-degrading and pathogenic microbes).

From this graph, it can be seen that the pH of all soil samples is clearly alkalinized relative to the background (pH ≈ 7.74-7.97 and background = 7.12). The pH difference in the soil samples increased by 0.62-0.85 units - this indicates a significant change in soil chemistry. Some detergent/chemical waste and construction debris in household waste alkalize the soil. Ammonium and carbonates, which are formed during the decomposition of waste in landfills, also increase the pH of the soil. Increased soil pH negatively affects fertility, and microelements (Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu) transition to a less soluble form for plants, causing nutritional deficiency. Bonding and restriction with phosphorus can be observed.

Figure 1. Soil pH of soils around household landfills

If the pH is high, the nitrogen state may lead to more ammonia volatilization than ammonia. Heavy metals (Pb, Cd, Bi, Ni), accumulating in the soil as a result of household waste and industrial pollution, significantly affect the activity of soil microorganisms. The research results show that these metals reduce the biological diversity of microorganisms, reduce soil fertility, and disrupt the ecological balance.

Figure 2. Content of heavy metals in the soils around household waste disposal sites

Among these heavy metals, the most toxic are lead (Pb) and cadmium (Cd), which sharply reduce the number of bacteria, fungi, and actinomycetes, slow down enzymatic processes in the soil, and negatively affect the plant's food chain. Although bismuth (Bi) and nickel (Ni) have relatively less effect, at high concentrations they cause the development of beneficial microorganisms to stop. The graph shows the content of heavy metals (elements) Cd (cadmium), Bi (bismuth), Pb (lead), Ni (nickel). In the studies, the content of cadmium (Cd) in soil samples MCHJ -1.1 and MCHSHA-1.1, MCHSHi-1, MCHG'-1 changed in the amount of 0.11, 0.46, 0.08, 0.06 mg/kg, and it was found that the content of this substance exceeded the Clarke (0.13) only from the point MCHSHA-1.1. Cd increased significantly only in the MCHSHA-1.1 zone.

We can see that the amount of Bi (bismuth) in all soil samples exceeds the Clarke value. MCHJ -1.1 -0.43, MCHSHA-1.1-0.46, MCHSHi-1-0.38, MCHG'-0.44, and the Clarke value is 0.009. In the soils around household landfills, the Clarke of bismuth increases 50 times in the southern part, 52 times in the eastern part, 42 times in the northern part, and 49 times in the western

part. Different levels of pollution on different sides of the landfill depend on the activity of natural factors. This pollution requires reclamation of the territory's soils. Based on the results, it can be assumed that there is general pollution in the area. It was established that the content of lead (Pb) at all points exceeds the Clarke value (16) by 2-3.5 times. MCHG-1 and MCHSHa-1.1 increased by 3.5 times, MCHJ-1.1 and MCHSHi-1 - by 2 times, and it was noted that these indicators are close to the background soil indicators. The Pb content is also higher than the background and Clarke. We can see that the nickel content at all points exceeds the background value by 2-4 times. This indicates a high nickel content and soil contamination in the region. The research results show that the most polluted points are MCHJ-1.1 - Cd, Bi, Pb, MPCH-1 - Pb, Ni are very high, the least polluted point: MCHG-1 Bi is high. The content of the element Bi sharply increased in all soil samples. It was also noted that the content of Pb and Ni in almost all samples exceeds the background value.

In conclusion, the soils of this region are highly contaminated with heavy metals Bi, Pb, Ni. This indicates that the soils of the region are under environmental threat. Among the territories, points MCHSHA-1.1 and MCHG-1 stand out as the most dangerous. When cleaning these soils, biological cleaning methods, including bioremediation (soil cleaning with the help of microorganisms) and the use of biochar, help to neutralize heavy metals. Agroecological measures such as soil pH regulation and composting are required. In general, heavy metals have a strong negative impact on soil fertility, which threatens the stability of the agroecosystem. Therefore, protecting soil from metal pollution and ensuring environmental safety is one of the important strategic issues.

REFERENCES

1. Tokhtasin Abdrakhmanov, Zafarjon Jabbarov, Gulkhayo Atoyeva, Sardor Sayitov, Inna Cabelkova and Lubos Smutka. Changes in the Number of Volatile Components in the Soil Under the Influence of Household Waste. *Acta Montanistica Slovaca*, Volume 28 (2023), 3; P. 535-542. DOI: 10.46544/AMS.v28i3.0.
2. Šmejkalová M., Mikanová O., Boruvka L. Effects of heavy metal concentrations on biological activity of soil micro-organisms. *PLANT SOIL ENVIRON.*, 49, 2003 (7): 321–326.
3. Nafiu Abdu, Aliyu A. Abdullahi., Aisha Abdulkadir. Heavy metals and soil microbes. *Environmental Chemistry Letters*. Volume 15, (2017) , pp 65–84.
4. Zafarjon Jabbarov, Gulkhayo Atoyeva, Sardor Sayitov, Rakhmon Kurvantaev, Nodira Khakimova, Samad Makhhammadiev, Yunus Kenjaev, Dilafruz Makhkamova, Bakhrom Jobborov, Gulchekhra Nabiyeva, Najmiddin Nurgaliev, Malika Aliboyeva, Salomat Zakirova. Study on the soil pollution condition around the domestic wastewater. *E3S Web of Conferences* 497, 03005 (2024), -Pp. 9. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202449703005>.
5. Wang Yuan-peng, Shi Ji-yan, Lin Qi, Chen Xin-cai, Chen Ying-xu. Heavy metal availability and impact on activity of soil microorganisms along a Cu/Zn contamination gradient. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*. Volume 19, Issue 7, 2007, Pages 848-853.
6. Hiroyuki Hattori. Influence of Heavy Metals on Soil Microbial Activities. *Soil Sci Plant Nut1.*, 38 (1), 93-100, 1992.
7. Wen-Jing Gong, Zi-Fan Niu., Xing-Run Wang and He-Ping Zhao. Open Access Article How the Soil Microbial Communities and Activities Respond to Long-Term Heavy Metal

- Contamination in Electroplating Contaminated Site. *Microorganisms* 2021, 9(2), 362; <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9020362>.
8. Bo Tang, Haopu Xu, Fengmin Song, Hongguang Ge, Siyu Yue. Effects of heavy metals on microorganisms and enzymes in soils of lead–zinc tailing ponds. *Environmental Research*. Volume 207, 2022, 112174.
 9. Xue-Ting Bai, Jichen Vang, Xailiang Dong, Jia-Min Chen vaYuan Ge. Relative importance of soil properties and heavy metals/metalloids to modulate microbial community and activity at a smelting site. *Journal of Soils and sediments*. Volume 21, pages 1–12, (2021).
 10. Yangbin Mao., Haifeng Tan., Maomao Wang, Tianheng Jiang., Hewen Wei., Wenping Xu., Qiong Jiang., Hexigeduleng Bao., Yanfei Ding., Feijuan Wang., Cheng Zhu. Research Progress of Soil Microorganisms in Response to Heavy Metals in Rice. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* Vol 70/Issue 28. 2022
 11. Michaela F. The Influence of Heavy Metals on Soil Biological and Chemical Properties. *Soil & Water Res.*, 5, 2010 (1): 21–27.